

Asadova Manzura Akhatovna*Teacher of Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management at the Tashkent Research Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5976664>**SCIENTIFIC SUBSTANTIATION OF AGRICULTURAL LAND ASSESSMENT**

Annotation: *this article is based on research on the scientific basis of agricultural land assessment.*

Key words: *scientific, substantiation, agricultural, land, assessment.*

In order to increase the productivity of irrigated lands of the Republic and regions, to combat the processes of degradation and to obtain high yields of agricultural crops, it is recommended to introduce the following science-based measures:

From agrochemical measures - it is advisable to apply 150-160 kg of nitrogen per hectare, 125-140 kg of phosphorus fertilizers per hectare on strongly saline irrigated lands due to a 50% decrease in the effectiveness of fertilizers under the influence of soil salts, salinity. It is also recommended to apply mineral fertilizers at a high rate near the surface of non-plowed groundwater in the fall and spring plowing on two-tiered plows.

It is recommended to apply 70% of phosphorus fertilizers, 50% of potassium fertilizers and 20-30 tons of organic fertilizers per hectare or 15-20 tons of compost in the form of compost before autumn plowing on irrigated lands. Also, given the shortage of phosphorus and potassium mineral fertilizers, relatively inexpensive organo-mineral fertilizers made from non-traditional agro-ores (bentonite, glauconite, etc.) and based on them in order to enrich the soil with organic matter and improve their chemical, physical, agrochemical, ecological and reclamation conditions it is recommended to use composts, phosphorite, phosphogypsum from raw materials and wastes containing nutrients;

Agrotechnical measures such as land leveling, weeding, drip irrigation save up to 50% of water and reduce other agro-technical measures. It is expedient to introduce rotational and short-rotation sowing, to grow saline-resistant, perennial forage, legumes, oilseeds and melons and gourds on the basis of high agro-technical requirements in areas with low quality of cotton;

Deep loosening of local fertilizers (manure - 20 t / ha) on low-yielding, cotton yield not exceeding 8-12 quintals, reclamation and redevelopment period 6-8 years, difficult reclamation, saline, requiring complex agro-technical and reclamation measures (50-60 cm), it is necessary to wash the brine quality, sow siderate crops and plow in the form of blue mass;

In order to maintain and increase the fertility of organic, organomineral and mineral soils in areas with reduced humus and nutrients in the soil, it is necessary, first of all, to ensure the placement of only one type of crop in one contour. Because. Placing the same type of crop in a single contour has the convenience of carrying out applied agro-technical and other activities. This ensures that the activities performed on each contour

are performed simultaneously, in the same way and by technical means. In addition, irrigation water is saved when planting one type of crop in one contour. The placement of cotton and cereals (wheat) in the introduction of the rotation system on irrigated lands of medium and high productivity (above 40 points) in the placement of agricultural crops, taking into account the type of previous crop. Vegetables, melons, oilseeds, legumes, fodder and other crops, as well as orchards and vineyards should be planted on lands with a fertility of less than 40 points. In areas with sufficient water supply, mainly cotton and grain crops, as well as planning for the cultivation of secondary and intermediate crops, placement of moist crops (rice, millet, white corn, mung bean) on saline soils with varying degrees of excess moisture. Since nitrogen is an integral component of proteins, nucleic acids, chlorophyll and enzymes, it plays a key role in plant life activities. Plants assimilate nitrogenous substances in the soil and form proteins from them. Large amounts of Nitrogen accumulate in the soil due to microorganisms that convert free Nitrogen in the air into Nitrogen compounds. It is found in the soil mainly in the form of four different compounds: humus nitrogen, ammonium salts, nitrates (NO₃), protein organic nitrogen (incompletely decomposed plant residues) and their by-products - amino acids, peptides, amides and amines. Nitrogen can be divided into three groups according to the solubility of organic compounds in the soil: water-soluble, soluble when hydrolyzed by dilute acid, and insoluble when hydrolyzed by dilute acid.

Nitrogen, which belongs to the insoluble group, is less mobile and does not absorb well into plants. Approximate amount of total nitrogen in some soils of Central Asia: in light gray soils (plowed layer) - 0.04-0.07%, in typical gray soils that have been irrigated for a long time - 0.10-0.15%, and in meadow soils - 0.20-0.50%. Nitrogen, which belongs to the group of irrigated farmers of Central Asia, is less mobile and does not absorb well into plants. Approximate amount of total nitrogen in some soils of Central Asia: in light gray soils (plowed layer) - 0.04-0.07%, in typical gray soils that have been irrigated for a long time - 0.10-0.15%, and in meadow soils - 0.20-0.50%. Nitrogen reserves in the soil are not sufficient for high yields in irrigated farming regions of Central Asia, so nitrogen fertilizers are applied here.

REFERENCES:

- 1.Khamidov F. R. et al. The Role of Peasant Farms and Homestead Lands in The Development of Agriculture //Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT. – 2021. – T. 3. – C. 5-8.
- 2.Karimov, E. K. (2020). STATUS OF LAND FOR AGRICULTURE AND EFFICIENT USE OF THEM. JOURNAL AGRO PROTSSESSING, (SPECIAL ISSUE).